

Removal of Time from Constant Momentum Scenarios Equivalent to A Conserved Quantum Probability in Space?

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In a previous note (1), we suggested that the quantum free particle wavefunction (or probability) $\exp(ipx)$ follows from an attempt to create a probability function which guarantees conservation of momentum.

In this note, we start with the classical idea of momentum which depends on rest mass and velocity, which seems to imply that a clock is needed as part of the measurement tools. Momentum, however, has the property that the same value may be created by different m_0, v pairs and is proportional to impulse. Impulse may be measured without using a clock it seems and so a dynamic variable, p , is associated with a nondynamic (no time needed) measurement. The problem, however, is that to measure the impulse one needs to know the x position (one dimension) of the particle and this requires following the particle in time. If a collision occurs between p_1 and p_2 , one needs to know the time because a total impulse must be measured before the time and after to ensure conservation of momentum. Thus, the statement that the measurement of p does not require a clock does not seem to hold unless one really considers the full implications of removing time.

We argue that removing time introduces a flux probability type picture, i.e. the particle can be at any x (with the same probability seemingly), but flux suggests a conservation of some sort in space, i.e. p and x should not disappear. In other words, for a single particle one considers its past, present and future because there is no clock to distinguish between these. This is like a steady stream situation, but that situation contains many particles.

This is made physically manifest if one has a sharp change in p at a given x_0 as in one dimensional reflection-refraction. It is not enough to say that for $x < x_0$, there is one p and the same probability to be at any x and for $x > x_0$, the same condition holds. A space only picture (no time) requires a conservation of probability flux (which is a function of x and p), but in keeping with an overall constant probability in space at least for single p considerations. Thus, it is the removal of time in constant p scenarios which forces one to adopt the probability flux picture of quantum mechanics (i.e. $\exp(ipx)$). This probability flux picture holds even if one has a single particle which clearly has different p values at different times. The flux scenario is the price to pay for removing time. The removal of time follows from the classical statement that time is not needed to determine the value of p , i.e. one only requires an impulse measurement.

The Root of $\exp(ipx)$ in Classical Impulse?

Impulse is a classical concept and is proportional to the change in momentum in Newtonian mechanics. If a particle with momentum p (and necessarily velocity) changes to $p=0$, then impulse is proportional to p . Both relativistically and nonrelativistically, momentum depends on m_0 (rest mass) and v . V (velocity) requires a clock for measurement, so at first glance one would expect the dynamic variable p to require a clock for measurement. The problem with this is that different m_0, v values yield the same p and all one needs is to make an impulse measurement. One does not need to measure velocity using a clock (and ruler) because one

would have to measure rest mass as well in that case. A single impulse measurement should suffice (e.g. using a spring). There might seem to be a catch, however, because one needs to measure impulse when the particle strikes a target or spring and then one needs to know the time that this occurs. If a particle, however, is moving in one dimension, from the left, one may place a spring at an x point to the right and take an impulse measurement. No clock is needed because it is irrelevant at which time the particle hits the spring. Different m_0, v pairs yielding the same p would hit at different times.

Removal of Time for a Constant Momentum and the Concept of Probability Flux

If one removes time from the picture of a constant momentum in one dimension, it seems one should be able to make an impulse measurement at any x . In other words, the particle is not followed in time so all of its (x,t) pairs are given equal footing, i.e. one seems to see the particle during its past, present and future. This is equivalent to a flux picture in which one has a steady stream of particles and does not worry about the identity of the particle.

A flux picture, however, is usually associated with conservation. Here one has a single particle and no clock so there is no usual flux (which depends on counting a particle or energy etc per second). The question then becomes: What is conserved? The particle with constant p is associated with the same probability to be at any x , but this statement holds for any p . One may ask: What happens if p suddenly changes at a given x_0 ? It has p_1 for $x < x_0$ and p_2 for $x > x_0$ and one uses the steady stream picture. Furthermore, the particle before and after is linked to the same probability in x .

At first it seems that by choosing a fixed x_0 , one chooses a fixed time, but if one has a continuity of probability flux then the actual value of x_0 is irrelevant. Given that one does not consider time at all, one could in principle have a single particle with p_1 change to p_2 at x_0 or reflect with $-p_1$ at x_0 . Furthermore, a flux probability $F(p_1, x)F(p_2, x) = F(p_1 + p_2, x)$ (one dimension). This suggests a power law and to include x and to have a link with constant probability for all x , one has:

$$\exp(ipx) = \text{probability flux} \quad ((1))$$

In (1), we started with the idea that one must enforce conservation of probability. This condition $F(p_1)F(p_2) = F(p_1 + p_2)$ leads to a power law $\exp(p)$, but no x appears. X was introduced together with $-p$ final to create orthogonality in space.

Here, we argue that removing time is equivalent to introducing a conserved flux probability. For a single particle, a flux concept means that the particle may be at any x because one does not know time. In other words, one has past, present and future all presented in one scheme because there is no time to distinguish between these. X should be present because one may distinguish between x points. Furthermore, the change in p at a given x_0 suggests a presence of x as well. We have argued that $\exp(ipx)$ allows for a p and x behaviour to be present, but the physical consequence is a wavelength \hbar/p . (Here \hbar is a constant with proper units..)

The form $\exp(ipx)$ is critical to the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem because there is p_1 for $x < x_0$ and p_2 for $x > x_0$. At x_0 , there must not only be continuity of probability, but of

momentum probability and this requires introducing a reflected beam. In a steady state picture (or present, past and future together for all possible physical scenarios), one has:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=x_0 \quad ((2a))$$

$$\text{And } Ap \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{at } x=x_0 \quad ((2b))$$

Given $A=1$, ((2a)) and ((2b)) allow one to solve for B, C whereas a constant probability scheme does not.

The Question of Conservation of Momentum

Physically an interaction occurs at a given x and t . We argued above that one does not need time to measure p but it seems that with conservation of momentum during an interaction, one needs a clock because one has to measure total momentum before and after the interaction. To remove time, one cannot simply state that the interaction may occur at any x at any time. There has to be a before and after in time. As argued in (1), the way to handle this is to use $-p_3-p_4$ for the final momenta and p_1+p_2 for the initial. This then leads to $\exp(-i(p_3+p_4)x) \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) = 1$ for all x . In other words, this is no longer a flux, but a definite constant probability. If p_3+p_4 and p_1+p_2 , however, do not match, then the combination represents a flux which is on average 0 for each component. Integrated over x , however, it yields 0 because one is considering an OR situation of the interaction occurring at x_1 or x_2 or x_3 etc. One cannot have one x point because there is no time in the picture.

For one dimensional reflection-refraction there is one physical x_0 in the picture, but this has nothing to do with time. There is a steady stream $\exp(ipx)$ for $x < 0$ (as well as $\exp(-ipx)$) and $\exp(ip_2x)$ for $x > x_0$.

Implications for the Classical Action

Given that p may be measured without a clock by performing an impulse measurement in x , we suggest that the classical action for constant p , should separate into two pieces, one a function of p and x and the other, a function of E and t . Given $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + mc^2$ ($c=1$), if one knows p and m_0 , one may obtain E , but knowing p and m_0 means knowing v which reflects a clock measurement. This is what arises as $-Et+px$ is the classical action for constant p in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases.

Examples of Time Removal in Quantum Mechanics

If one considers the time-independent Schrodinger equation, then $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are included in the wavefunction because there is no time in this scheme. That does not mean that physically the particle does not move to the left or right in time. The removal of time leads to a conserved probability flux scheme which allows one to solve problems. Furthermore, this probability scheme is linked to wavelength units, \hbar/p , in which there is certain p , but only a probability for x .

A second example is 2-slit interference. One writes an $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ for each slit to a fixed point on a screen. Time of arrival from each slit may be completely different, but with time removed, this is irrelevant. One only considers the conserved probability flux scheme.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that because the classical dynamical variable momentum can be measured without a clock due to impulse, even though it contains m_0 and v and the latter requires a clock, one may consider a p - x scheme for constant p in which no time appears. The catch is that in general to measure impulse one has to know where the particle is at a certain time and that requires a clock. Thus, it seems that one considers all past, present and future x points in order to remove time. This leads to the notion of a flux probability in p, x . At the same time the idea of equal probability as all x points must apply and $F(p_1, x)F(p_2, x) = F(p_1 + p_2, x)$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. To see that this is really a flux probability linked with conservation (probability and momentum probability) must be conserved, one may consider the problem of one dimensional reflection-refraction. Conservation of probability flux and momentum probability flux cannot occur if one only has $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$, one must introduce a reflected flux. Given that time is removed, $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$ appear as if they occur at the same (but there is no time in this picture). This scenario of a conserved probability flux $\exp(ipx)$ with time removed allows one to enforce conservation of momentum (albeit by integrating over x because an interaction may occur at any x), 2-slit interference etc and one dimensional reflection-refraction.

In short, the mathematical function p (momentum) is of physical relevance because it is proportional to impulse which does not require a clock for measurement (even though p must have a v which does require a clock). Different m_0, v pairs may yield the same p . It is the description of p in x without any time present which leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability flux which is linked to conservation (continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ (with $B\exp(-ipx)$) and $p\exp(ipx)$ at junctions in which p changes as well as conservation of momentum.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in Terms of Probability, Space and Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)